

Club convergence in innovation activity across European regions

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The goal of this paper is to analyse the innovation activity convergence process across European regions from 2002 to 2012. A novel methodology developed by Phillips and Sul (2007, 2009) that allows either detection of overall convergence or endogenous identification of groups of regions was applied. The results support the club convergence hypothesis for explaining the convergence process of Europe's regions during the period analysed and seven innovation convergence clubs were identified. In addition, the research results indicate that initial regional R&D expenditure is the most relevant factor driving the formation of the convergence clubs after controlling for the effects of regional structural characteristics.

Keywords: Club convergence; innovation activity; European regions; *log t* test

JEL codes: O33, O47

1. Introduction

Convergence across European territories has attracted interest from European policymakers for several decades. At present, the European Union (EU) aims for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, establishing the consolidation of knowledge and innovation as engines of European economic growth (European Commission, 2010). The relationship among knowledge, innovation, and economic growth in European regions has been well established in several studies (Badinger and Tondl, 2003; Basile, 2008; Guastella and Timpano, 2016). Most of the empirical literature that has focused on regional growth and dynamics of innovation has emphasized the major role technological gaps play in the existence of disparities in per capita income and productivity across Europe's regions (Fagerberg and Verspagen, 1996; Rodríguez-Pose and Crescenzi, 2008; Chapman and Meliciani, 2017). These differences in technological capabilities in the EU have been deepened by the enlargement process (Filippetti and Peyrache, 2013; Paci and Marrocu, 2013). The evidence suggests that European regions

follow a dual pattern (center-periphery) in relation to innovation activity. For instance, Foddi and Usai (2013) found that the most efficient regions are located in the centre and north of Europe and the least efficient ones in peripheral areas. The complexity of innovation patterns and the relevance of regional contextual conditions have also been pointed out in relation to innovation patterns across European regions (Camagni and Capello, 2013; Capello and Lenzi, 2013). In this context, if disparities in technological capabilities play a key role to explain the income disparities, a deep knowledge of the dynamics of convergence in innovation activity becomes relevant and can shed new light on income convergence processes among European regions.

This paper employs the panel convergence methodology developed by Phillips and Sul (2007) to analyse the pattern of convergence in innovation activity across European regions over the period 2002-2012. In addition, it investigates the role that diverse innovation determinants may play in explaining the patterns of convergence using an ordered logit model.

This study makes two main contributions to the empirical literature. First, it represents a novel application of innovation data to the methodology developed by Phillips and Sul (2007), providing new evidence regarding the process of convergence in innovation activity among European regions. It allows the identification of groups of regions with similar patent growth paths during the period of analysis as well as the growth trajectory of each club. Second, it identifies important factors for explaining innovation convergence clubs.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 briefly discusses the theoretical foundations and most relevant empirical evidence related to the topic. Section 3 drafts the research strategy with special reference to the methodology, data, and identification

of convergence clubs. Section 4 analyses potential explanatory factors of club formation. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main conclusions.

2. Literature review

This section describes the theoretical background and the empirical evidence on which our empirical analysis is based. The literature review is split into three parts. Section 2.1 discusses the theoretical background for innovation convergence clubs, identifying factors that could explain this convergence pattern. Section 2.2 emphasizes the spatial dimension of innovation; and finally, section 2.3 shows the empirical evidence regarding the main factors that explain innovation activity in the European regions.

2.1 Innovation convergence clubs

Economic growth is a requirement for economic convergence among economies; thus, convergence processes have been analysed within growth theories framework. The growth theories emphasize the role of technological progress in economic growth from different perspectives. In the neoclassical growth models (Solow, 1956; Swan, 1956), technology progress is an exogenous process. Technology knowledge is assumed as a public good—that all economies have access to the same technology. Within this framework, the convergence process is based on the existence of decreasing returns in capital accumulation with economies tending to converge toward a single long-run steady state.

In endogenous growth models (Romer, 1986; Lucas, 1988), technological progress is endogenously determined, requiring investments in research and development and human capital. Innovation-driven growth models (Romer, 1990; Aghion and Howitt, 1992; Grossman and Helpman, 1994) emphasize the role of innovation efforts as a source of technological progress; the productivity level of a

country depends on its cumulative R&D effort and its stock of knowledge (Coe and Helpman, 1995). In endogenous growth models, technological knowledge is assumed as a possibly appropriable good, explaining the incentive to invest in innovative activities; and as a non-rival good, explaining aggregate increasing returns (Castellacci, 2007). Externalities created by knowledge spillovers are the most important source of sustainable growth in the long run (Koo, 2005). The differences in innovation capacity among economies appear as one of the basic explanations for persistent differences in economic performance from the endogenous growth perspective (Rodríguez-Pose and Crescenzi, 2008).

Several empirical studies have found the existence of income convergence clubs when analysing convergence across economies around the world, including European regions (Bartkowska and Riedl, 2012; von Lyncker and Thoennesen, 2016). The club convergence hypothesis (Azariadis and Drazen, 1990; Galor, 1996) suggests that economies that are similar in their structural characteristics converge toward one another in the long run only if they have similar initial conditions (Galor, 1996).

Growth models in the Schumpeterian tradition argue that differences in innovative ability and the absorptive capacity to imitate advanced foreign technologies of economies are potential sources of income polarization and convergence clubs (Castellacci, 2008). The technology-gap approach assumes that economic growth is the result of two forces that operate in opposition: innovation, which generates a technology gap; and diffusion and imitation, which tend to reduce it (Fagerberg, 1987). Therefore, technology can be both a convergence factor (by means of imitation) and a divergence factor (by means of innovation) of development levels (Verspagen, 2010). Countries with a lower technological level than more advanced countries can exploit their backward position and increase their growth rates through diffusion of international

technology by imitation (Faberger, 1987; Castellacci, 2007). The catching-up process depends on innovative efforts, but also on the innovative efforts of countries on the technological frontier (Faberger, 1987). The process of diffusion is costly, and the countries below the technological frontier to be successful in imitating advanced technology, need to have social and institutional capabilities (Castellacci, 2007).

Howitt (2000) developed a multi-country model in which innovation is a skill-intensive activity and the unique source of technological progress. Countries form two clubs: A group of countries will grow at the same pace as the countries on the technological frontier, while the other group, which do not innovate, will stagnate. In the convergence club model of Howitt and Mayer-Foulkes (2005) based on innovation-based growth theory, including technology transfer, both innovation and imitation are costly and skill-intensive activities. In the model, countries are clustered into three groups: R&D leaders, implementation, and stagnation, depending on their technological capabilities. The implementation and R&D leaders converge to the same growth path but they do not reach the same levels of productivity. The absorptive capacity of technologically lagged regions can be eroded by human capital externalities and fishing-out effects that hinder their catch-up processes.

Empirical evidence in line with the above growth models supports the existence of technology clubs for different sets of countries with different growth dynamics (Castellacci 2008; Castellacci and Archibugi, 2008; Stöllinger, 2013). For example, Stöllinger (2013) analysed a large sample of countries categorized into three technology clubs—innovation, imitation, and stagnation—depending on their innovation ability and absorptive capacity. The author found that the effect of the technology gap on growth was stronger for the imitation club. Castellacci (2008) identified three technology clubs—advanced, followers, and marginalized—from a sample of 149 economies

during the 1990s. The researcher found that technology clubs have shown different dynamics of technological change over time. Advanced countries on the technological frontier have grown rapidly; countries in the followers club have experienced a slow technological catching-up, gradually closing their technology gap with advanced countries; and members of the marginalized club have experienced a slow process of catching up in terms of absorptive capacity, but their technology gap vis-à-vis the other clubs regarding their innovative ability has increased. Castellacci and Archibugi (2008) identified the same three technology clubs as those in the previous study, drawing from a large sample of developed and developing countries. During the 1990s, the followers club had a rapid technological catching-up process in all indicators, including innovative capabilities regarding advanced countries; the marginalized club experienced an increase in its innovative capabilities gap regarding the rest of the clubs and slow convergence for all indicators with respect to followers.

Technology clubs have been found in European regions. For instance, Verspagen, (1999) analysed the existence of regional clubs during the 1980s, finding evidence of four economic clubs and four technology clubs but with no simple connection between the two types of clubs. In another paper (Verspagen, 2010), the author analysed technology and development clusters in European regions at the beginning of the 2000s. The results suggested a spatial hierarchy of European regions comprising four groups of regions with important differences in innovation performance and growth dynamics. Similarly, Capello and Lenzi (2013) noted the existence of different innovation modes across European regions with different growth benefits. Specifically, the authors found five clusters of European regions namely, science-based area, applied science area, smart creative diversification area, smart technological application area and imitative innovation area.

Bearing in mind all the above theoretical aspects and empirical evidence on important differences in technological capabilities across European regions, with groups of regions characterized by different levels of innovative ability and absorptive capacity and different growth dynamics, the expectation is that innovation activity in European regions might follow a convergence club pattern rather than a full convergence. That is, regions with similar innovation ability and absorptive capacity will converge into specific technology clubs depending on their starting point, ranging from advanced innovative clubs to technologically marginalized clubs. Innovation activity of follower clubs might grow at the same rate as that of advanced clubs, but it does not mean that they will reach the same level of innovation activity.

2.2 Spatial nature of innovation activity

The theoretical background detailed above enables us to identify factors that may explain innovation convergence clubs. The revision of these models informs the important factors as determinants of innovation ability (R&D expenditure), and of absorptive capacity (human capital, knowledge spillovers, and social and institutional conditions).

In this section, we focus on spatial factors of innovation activity. Presently, it is commonly accepted that innovation is a territorially embedded process that is affected by the social and institutional characteristics of each space (Rodríguez-Pose, 1999; Rodríguez-Pose and Crescenci, 2008; Capello and Lenzi, 2013; Capello and Lenzi, 2014).

The view of innovation as a territorially embedded process is to a great extent based on successful examples of some innovative territorial agglomerations (Doloreux and Parto, 2005) such as industrial districts (Becattini, 1987), learning regions (Morgan,

1997), or systems of innovation (Cooke, 1998). Innovation activity, like economic activity, tends to be spatially concentrated, especially in places that have a well-developed technological infrastructure (Feldman and Florida, 1994). Innovation is facilitated in situations of geographic concentration and proximity; the concentration of economic activities of related firms in a cluster facilitates knowledge spillovers¹ and stimulates various forms of adaptation, learning, and innovation (Doloreux and Parto, 2005).

Localization theories explain not only that knowledge spills over, but also why spillovers decay with distance (Audretsch and Feldman, 2004). The basic explanation for knowledge spillovers is related to the externalities associated with knowledge due to its non-exclusive and non-rival use (Arrow, 1962). The explanation of why knowledge externalities are spatially bounded is that knowledge or, more specifically, tacit knowledge, as opposed to information, is expensive to acquire, to reproduce, or to transmit over long distances (Audretsch and Feldman, 2004). Knowledge spillovers can be local or can be generated outside the borders of the locality or region, but as we stated previously, distance matters in spillovers. The capacity of knowledge spillovers to travel increases with geographic proximity (Rodríguez-Pose and Crescenzi, 2008). From an operational point of view, in spatial econometric models, geographic connections between regions are introduced through weights matrices, mainly through contiguity weight and distance weight matrices, showing small differences in the way spillovers affect the pairs of regions (Baumont, et al., 2000).

¹ Cohen and Levinthal (1989) define knowledge spillovers as all the original and valuable knowledge, obtained from the research process that becomes publicly accessible.

2.3 Explanatory factors of regional innovation: Empirical evidence

In the literature on innovation and technological change at the regional level, a number of empirically oriented studies have addressed factors that determine regional innovation activity and explain cross-regional differences in innovation performance. Most studies have applied the knowledge production function framework (Griliches, 1979) for this purpose. This approach assumes that innovation output depends on R&D expenditure, but it has been augmented to include regional resources affecting regional innovation output (Ó hUallacháin and Leslie, 2007; Crescenzi and Jaax, 2017).

In the case of European regions, diverse studies have applied regional knowledge production function when analysing regional innovation activity, stressing the role regional innovation efforts as well as regional characteristics and the surrounding areas play in innovation output. A common result of these empirical studies is that innovation activity is influenced by internal factors (such as spending on R&D, human capital, agglomeration economies, and economic structure) and by spillover effects, especially from geographically proximate regions (Moreno et al., 2005a; Ó hUallacháin and Leslie, 2007; Foddi and Usai, 2013; Marrocu et al., 2013; Charlot et al., 2015). For example, Moreno et al. (2005a) analysed the spatial distribution of innovation activity across 175 European regions (EU-17) from 1978 to 2001. They found that internal regional factors such as R&D expenditure and agglomeration economies, as well as innovation activity of other regions and national institutions, influenced regional knowledge production. Marrocu et al. (2013) investigated the technological activities of 276 European regions (EU-29) in the 2005-2007 period. The results emphasized the roles human capital and R&D play in explaining the production of technological knowledge across regions. Their findings showed that the production of patents is higher within manufacturing sectors, while agglomeration effects are not

significant. They also found that proximity factors such as technological and geographical proximity matter for innovation activity across European regions to a greater extent than other proximity dimensions. Charlot et al. (2015) analysed innovation output across 169 European regions (EU-25) from 1995 to 2004. Their analysis highlighted the existence of a high complementarity between R&D and human capital, but stated that a critical mass of both factors is needed for regions to benefit from innovation inputs.

3. Convergence in innovation activity across European regions

3.1 Methodology: The log t test

The econometric method we used to test the convergence of innovation among European regions is based on the Phillips and Sul (2007) *log t* test. This methodology has clear advantages over alternative methods. First, while other methodologies group the economies a priori without using any specific methodology, thus limiting the results, the *log t* test does so endogenously, discovering groups by unspecified factors that determine the formation of the convergence clubs. Second, this methodology is based on a cross-sectional distribution, a sigma convergence instead of a beta convergence, modeling the structure of the data panel as a nonlinear relationship in which the coefficients may vary through time, showing that the asymptotic properties are well defined. The test is a process of regression as well as a grouping that does not depend on eventual assumptions about the stationary trend of the variables examined (Monfort et al., 2013). In addition, with this methodology it is possible to estimate the speed of the convergence parameter, which makes it possible to empirically distinguish relative convergence.

The methodology details are provided as follows:

Let $\{X_{it}\}$ be a data panel for variable X_{it} , $i=1, \dots, N$ and $t=1, \dots, T$ where N refers to the number of regions and T is the number of years. Phillips and Sul (2007) propose a nonlinear time-varying factor model for testing the convergence hypothesis and the identification of convergence clubs. In this way, the variable under study, X_{it} , is explained by two components:

$$\log X_{it} \approx \varphi_i \mu_t, \quad (1)$$

where φ_i is the component containing idiosyncratic factors of each region, while μ_t represents the common stochastic trends.

Thus, Phillips and Sul (2007, 2009) introduce a cross-sectional analysis as well as an analysis of heterogeneous time series in the parameters of a neoclassical growth model in order to take into account the heterogeneity of the transition temporary variable analyzed. In this formulation, factor loading φ_i measures the distance between X_{it} and common factor μ_t .

This idea leads to the following procedure:

Given $\{X_{it}\}$, then the following steps are performed:

First, for each time t , the mean value is calculated, and each individual value is compared with the obtained average value

$$h_{it} = \frac{X_{it}}{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N X_{it}}{N}} \quad (2)$$

On the sequel, we work with the panel of h_{it} (2), in place of the initial panel X_{it} .

Second, for each time t , the variance of the values h_{it} is calculated using the following formula:

$$H_t = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (h_{it} - 1)^2}{N} \quad (3)$$

The reason for comparing each value with 1 is that if there was convergence, all these values should converge to 1 (transition curves).

In order to specify the null hypothesis of convergence, Phillips and Sul (2007) formulated idiosyncratic element φ_{it} as:

$$\varphi_{it} = \varphi_i + \frac{\sigma_i \varepsilon_{it}}{L(t)t^\alpha} \quad (4)$$

Where φ_i is fixed, σ_i is an idiosyncratic scale parameter, ε_{it} are iid $N(0,1)$ across i , $L(t)$ is a slowly varying function such as $\log(t)$ ($L(t) \rightarrow \infty$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$) and α denotes the speed of convergence.

The null hypothesis of convergence is formulated as:

$$H_0: \varphi_i = \varphi \text{ and } \alpha \geq 0$$

against the alternative of convergence

$$H_A: \varphi_i \neq \varphi \text{ for all } i \text{ or } \alpha < 0.$$

The absolute convergence hypothesis assumes that H_t tends to zero. To study it, if we consider the following model to fit the data:

$$\log\left(\frac{H_t}{H_1}\right) - 2\log(\log t) = \alpha + \beta \log t + u_{it} \quad t = [rT], [rT] + 1, \dots, T, \quad (5)$$

with r suitably chosen,² if $\beta < 0$, the absolute convergence hypothesis is rejected. Based on Monte Carlo simulations, Phillips and Sul (2007) suggest using $r=0.3$ for sample sizes below $T=50$.

The next step is to measure, with a suitable statistic, the degree of reliability of the value obtained for β .

If the global convergence hypothesis is rejected, then it goes on to identify possible convergence clubs. To this end, an iterative algorithm developed by Phillips and Sul (2007) is applied so that the results of this algorithm have a significance level of 5%. The iterative procedure to identify convergence clubs is summarized in four steps:

Step 1 (sort the data panel cross-section): When $T \rightarrow \infty$, the convergence, even inside each club, is most evident in the latest observations of the series. For this reason, the first step consists in ordering the regions in the panel data from highest to lowest based on the observations of the most recent period, in our case 2012.

Step 2 (formation of convergence clubs): To form the first club, take the k highest regions (with $2 \leq k < N$) in the last column in the panel (corresponding to 2012 in the current case), and run the $\log t$ test of convergence, computing the convergence statistic t_k for this group. The optimal size k^* will be selected according to the criterion:

$$k^* = \arg \max_k \{t_k\} \text{ subject to } \min\{t_k\} > -1,65 \quad (6)$$

² The reason for using this factor r relies on the fact that the final columns of the panel are more important than the first ones.

The meaning of the critical value -1.65 ensures a level of significance of 5%.

This is done in this way for the first two regions, and if it does not meet the criterion, it is done with the second and third, and continued until a couple of regions meet the criterion. If this does not happen, we can conclude that there are no clubs of convergence in the data panel.

Step 3 (sift data to form clubs): If in the previous step two regions meet the established criterion/criteria, the process will continue, adding regions in the order they appear in the data panel, which is already sorted, while the data continue to meet the criterion/criteria. When it no longer meets the criterion, it has found the first club.

Step 4 (repeat and stop rule): Countries not selected in the first club form a complement group. With them we run the *log t* regression again and, if it converges, then these countries form a second club. If not, we repeat steps 1 to 3 in order to find successive clubs. These countries show divergent behavior if no core group can be found.

Likewise, Phillips and Sul (2007) propose modelling the transitional elements φ_{it} by building a relative measure of such coefficients. In this sense, from (2) we can write

$$h_{it} = \frac{x_{it}}{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_{it}}{N}} = \frac{\varphi_{it}}{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \varphi_{it}}{N}} \quad (7)$$

This measures the weighted coefficients φ_{it} in relation to the panel data so that the variable h_{it} is called the relative transition path, and traces an individual path for each region i relative to the average panel data. Thus, h_{it} measures the trajectory of each region or country i from the starting position relative to the path of common growth.

When there is common behavior in the path of growth between regions, $h_{it} = h_t$, it could find a convergence club between that group and, in the same way, could trace the path of common growth of the club on the panel data.

Studying convergence in a panel data set has several appealing features. Since the model traces an individual path for each region i relative to the average panel of data, we can distinguish empirically different degrees of convergence. The regression coefficient β measures the speed of convergence³ since $\beta = 2\alpha$.

3.2 Data

For testing convergence in innovation activity across European regions, we used patents per million people application at the European Patent Office (EPO) from Eurostat. The use of patents as a proxy for innovation activities has been widely recognized in the literature (Griliches, 1990; Acs et al., 2002; Jaffe and Trajtenberg, 2005; Crescenzi et al., 2007). Like any other indicator, the use of a patent indicator presents advantages and disadvantages (see, for example, Griliches, 1990; Archibugi and Pianta 1996; Guellec and de la Potterie, 2001; Belleflamme, 2006). In spite of its limitations, it is one of the most reliable indicators for analyzing innovation activity across regions (Sleuwaegen and Boiardia, 2014).

In this paper, we consider per capita European patent applications at EPO for 180 regions belonging to 26 European countries⁴ over the period 2002-2012. The sample is composed mainly of European Union regions at NUTS-2, but NUTS-1 and

³ See appendix B, Phillips and Sul (2007).

⁴ The sample covers EU-27 countries except Greece due to lack of available data.

NUTS-0 levels have been considered for some of them.⁵ Regions at NUTS-2 level were used for Austria, Czech Republic, France, Finland, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Slovakia, and Sweden; at NUTS-1 level for Belgium, Bulgaria, Germany, Romania, and the United Kingdom, and NUTS-0 (country) for Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, and Slovenia. The relation of regions appears in Appendix A.

3.3. Innovation convergence clubs identification

When the *log t* test was applied to patents per million inhabitants across European regions, the hypothesis of overall convergence was rejected at the 5% significance level. We then proceeded to the clustering mechanism to check the existence of subgroup convergence, and we identified 16 subgroups and four diverging regions. To test whether any of the original clusters can be united to shape larger convergence clubs, we ran the merging test procedure presented by Phillips and Sul (2009)⁶. Seven convergence clubs were identified; the members of each club are presented in Appendix B. Table 1 report the results for patents per capita for the convergence clubs. In addition, we show a graphic illustration of club membership in Figure 1. Therefore, we can conclude that there is no sign of patent convergence among the regions included in

⁵ The choice of units of analysis for each country is based on administrative and relevant governance for innovation policies and the available data. In this paper we follow similar criteria as previous works focused on innovative activity of European regions (e.g. Crescenzi, et al., 2007; Usai, 2011; Charlot et al., 2015).

⁶ Phillips and Sul (2009) propose a test for merging between clubs: taking the first and the second club and running the *log t* test, if the t-statistic is larger than -1.65 (5% significance level), it is assumed that both clubs form one. Then, the test is repeated by adding the following clubs until the convergence hypothesis is rejected by the t-statistic. Later, we began again with the last group that was rejected and proceeded in the same way.

the study; on the contrary, innovation activity shows a convergence club pattern in line with our expectations.

[Table 1 about here]

Clubs 1 and 2 are composed of a few regions, two and six, respectively; they are the regions that generate the largest number of patents per million inhabitants (543 and 364 on average, respectively). These regions demonstrate a very different behaviour from the rest with respect to convergence; in the *log t* test procedure they presented good cohesion (see statistics on Table 1), but they did not admit any additional region of the clubs resulting from the merger procedure with others regions suggested for application of the algorithm developed by Phillips and Sul (2009). Club 1 consists of one region of Austria (Vorarlberg) and one region of the Netherlands (Zeeland), while club 2 has one region from Finland (Helsinki-Uusimaa), two from Sweden (Stockholm and Sydsverige), two from Germany (Baden-Württemberg and Niederbayern), and one from Austria (Oberösterreich). These are the innovation leading European regions.

Club 3, with an average of 181.1 patents per million inhabitants, is made up of 20 regions. The composition is as follows. Three regions belong to Finland, which leaves this country in a relevant position since the remaining region belongs to club 2; seven belong to Germany, three to Austria, and two to Sweden (these are countries with a high participation in clubs with higher values of the variable studied); three belong to France (the region for Paris and two from the south of the country); two to Northern Italy; one to the Netherlands; and one to Denmark.

Clubs 4 and 5, with an average of 104.6 and 57.2 patents per million inhabitants, respectively, contain 31 and 30 regions, respectively. These regions are found in Spain, France, Italy, the United Kingdom, Sweden, Ireland, and Slovenia. It should be noted that the United Kingdom does not have any region in clubs 1, 2, or 3; its regions belong

to clubs 4 to 6. Spain and Italy have a large percentage of their territory in club 7, which is mainly observed in the south of both countries, giving these areas a convergence with the marginal clubs of the rest of Europe. Both Ireland and Slovenia converge in club 5. These regions present more moderate innovation activity than innovator clubs.

Clubs 6 and 7, with an average of 22 and 5.7 patents per million inhabitants, respectively, contain 45 and 40 regions, respectively, so they are the marginal clubs in terms of the convergence of the analysed variable. The regions that converge in these clubs belong mainly to Eastern countries (Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Hungary, Romania, and Bulgaria), to Portugal, and to the south of Spain and Italy, as we can see in Figure 1. These are the weakest innovative European regions.

[Figure 1 about here]

Some spatial characteristics of innovation activity can be deduced from the results obtained in the cluster analysis for the 180 regions studied. First, regions belonging to the same country tend to cluster together or belong to nearby club (Barro and Sala-i-Martin, 1991; Quah, 1996). This hypothesis is reinforced by the fact that clubs seem to have spatial correlation. The club formation seems to be spatially concentrated, which is confirmed by the Moran's I test statistic, which reaches the value 0.66 when we estimate for the club category variable—that is, regions belonging to the same club tend to cluster together. Apparently, there is a country effect, as we can see in Figure 1. With the exception of clubs 1 and 2, with only eight regions (two and six, respectively), the countries seem to be divided between those with regions in clubs 6 and 7, mainly those in Eastern Europe and Portugal, and those with regions in clubs 3, 4, and 5—the Nordic countries, France, Germany, Belgium, Austria, the United Kingdom, and Ireland. In Spain and Italy, in the south their regions belong to clubs 6

and 7—those with the lowest number of patents per million inhabitants—and in the north regions belong to clubs 4 and 5. Second, the regions located in the capital of the country usually belong to a club superior to the adjoining regions—see for example Stockholm, Île de France (including Paris), Inner London, Comunidad de Madrid (including Madrid), or Budapest. This could be due to agglomeration effects (Martin and Ottaviano, 2001).

Figure 2 illustrates the relative transition path of the seven different clubs calculated as the cross-sectional mean of the members of each club. Under the assumption of convergence for the full panel of regions, the relative transition path should tend to unity—all patents per million people of each region converge to the same level. As can be seen in Figure 2, the first five clubs remain above the average while clubs 6 and 7, the marginal ones, fall below the average. The relative transition paths of the seven clubs displayed in Figure 2 show a slight tendency to unite, suggesting a very soft tendency toward club convergence.

[Figure 2 about here]

The results of our empirical analysis lead to a classification of European regions according to their innovative activity in clubs similar to results proved in other studies (e.g., Verspagen, 1999; 2010; Capello and Lenzi, 2013). However, the classification results of our study are not directly comparable with these papers due to differences related to innovative performance indicators used, the period analysed, and the cluster methodology applied. Our study uses patents as the innovation indicator; the methodology applied allows us to determine endogenously groups of converging regions in their innovation activity without considering pre-established criteria, and allow us knowing the transition paths of each club over time.

Finally, the results of this study should be interpreted in line with its limitations. First, our analysis focuses on the convergence pattern in innovation activity rather on technological capabilities, which is a broad concept. Technological capabilities encompass various indicators related to innovation outputs as well as regional absorption capacity represented by available human capital and infrastructure. Second, although the use of patents as a proxy for innovative performance has been widely employed in the empirical literature, there are other forms of innovation that are not captured by patent counts.

4. Determinants of innovation club membership

4.1. Ordered logit model and data

This section establishes an econometric framework with which to explore the possible determinants of innovation club membership. Specifically, we analyse the role of explanatory factors of regional innovation activity in determining membership in an innovation club.

The nature of the dependent variable suggests the formulation and estimation of the ordered logit model, introduced by McKelvey and Zavoina (1975). In the ordered logit model, the dependent variable represents an ordinal outcome. Our outcome variable has seven categories, one for each previously identified innovation club (Section 3). Because clubs 1 and 2 have few observations, and to avoid estimation problems, we decided to merge them in a single club labelled Club1+Club2. Therefore, we have six categories for our dependent variable Club (Club1+Club2, Club 3, Club4, Club5, Club6 and Club7).

We assume that this variable can be classified as an ordinal variable since the alternatives (categories) can be ordered according to the converging patent level of

regions in each club. Although the categories for the outcome variable can be ordered, the distances between categories (clubs) are unknown. For this reason, the use of a linear regression model cannot be appropriated and an ordinal regression model should be used (Long and Freese, 2014).

The empirical model takes the following form:

$$y_i^* = X_i\beta + \varepsilon_i$$

where y_i^* is a latent variable that takes on ordinal values from 1 to 6. X_i represent a set of explanatory variables that captures factors influencing regional innovation (in the initial period), i indicates the region ($i=1, \dots, 176$)⁷, the column vector β corresponds to the regression coefficients and ε is a random error.

Our baseline specification assumes that errors have a logistic distribution with a mean of zero and a variance of $\pi^2/3$, meaning that the resulting ordered regression model can be referred to as a logit model. The estimation procedure is based on maximum likelihood (ML).

According to the club convergence hypothesis, regions converge to a common steady state if they have similar initial conditions and structural characteristics. The set of explanatory variables (X_i) were identified based on the empirical literature regarding the determinants of regional innovation activity, considering them as possible relevant factors for innovation convergence club formation. The details about explanatory variables are provided as follows.

⁷ Although we considered 180 European regions for identifying the existence of regional convergence clubs (Section 3.3); in the empirical model used for analysing the determinants of innovation club membership (Section 4), we only considered 176 regions because 4 regions show a divergent behaviour with respect to the convergence process.

The traditional factor explaining innovation output within the regional knowledge production function framework is regional R&D resources; the positive relationship between research and development expenditure and patenting activity is well known. We captured regional R&D investment by means of R&D measured as the total regional intramural R&D expenditure in all sectors, private and public, as a percentage of GDP. We consider R&D in the initial period as the conditioning variable similarly to other studies (Wang et al., 2014; Blanco et al, 2015).

Additional factors related to structural characteristics of regions and considered by the empirical literature as determinants of innovation activity (Ó hUallacháin and Leslie, 2007) have also been included in our model. Complementary to R&D, empirical papers have pointed out that a region's human capital endowment positively influences knowledge creation and affects the capacity to absorb and exploit knowledge generated outside the region (Foddi and Usai, 2013; Caragliu and Nijkamp, 2012; Kalapouti and Varsakelli, 2015). We capture the human capital of every region by the HC variable measured as the regional share of population with tertiary education (according to ISCED 5-6).

Empirical papers have also suggested that innovation activity as well as economic activity tend to cluster spatially (Audretsch and Feldman, 1996; Usai, 2011). Agglomeration economies act on economic and innovation outputs through different forces related to Marshallian externalities (Crescenzi et al., 2007). Empirical papers have established a positive link between agglomeration effects and patenting activity given to localized knowledge spillovers (Ponds et al., 2010). We capture possible agglomeration effects by means of DEN measured as population density; that is, inhabitants per Km², as customary in the literature. Due the high dispersion of this variable (see Appendix C) we include this variable in the logarithm form in our model.

Similarly, innovation activity tends to cluster more in industries where new economic knowledge plays an important role and knowledge spillovers are prevalent (Audrestch and Feldman, 1996; Marrocu et al., 2013). We capture the regional economic production pattern by means of GVA measured as the share of GVA generated by the industry sector at basic prices.

Along with intra-regional research efforts, several studies have suggested that spatial knowledge spillovers may explain regional differences in innovation performance across regions; that is, knowledge generated in one region may spill over and influence innovation activity in neighbouring regions (Usai, 2011; D'Agostino et al., 2013; Marrocu et al., 2013; Charlot et al., 2015; Kalapouti and Varsakelli, 2015). SPI is included to account for interregional knowledge spillovers; it is measured by mean of $WxR\&D$. The term $WxR\&D$ is the spatial lag of R&D where W is a weight matrix referring to a first-order contiguity matrix based on adjacency.⁸ It takes the value 1 for bordering regions and 0 otherwise.

Finally, we consider that institutional effects control by country membership. We capture unobserved national factors such as laws, regulations, culture, polices, etc., common to all regions of the same country by means of INS. This variable reflects the state of institutional development at the country level⁹. The data were obtained from the “Global Competitiveness Report 2002–2003” published by the World Economic Forum. Higher values indicate a more negative position of the country regarding this indicator.

⁸ W can take several forms; the most general is the physical contiguity matrix (Moreno et al., 2005b), which has been used in previous studies at the regional level (see, for example, Moreno et al., 2006; Bartkowska & Riedl, 2012; D'Agostino et al., 2013).

⁹ This variable has been previously used in the empirical literature by Sleuwaegen and Boiardi (2014) to proxy the effect of the institutional framework on regional patenting activity.

All explanatory variables considered in the model were measured at the beginning of the period of analysis. Data were collected from Regional Statistics Eurostat. A summary of descriptive statistics for the variables is presented in Appendix C.

4.2. Results from an ordered logit model

According to Table 2, and in line with the growth empirics (Bartkowska and Riedl, 2012; von Lyncker and Thoennessen, 2016), the initial conditions, proxied in this study by R&D, play a significant role in explaining club membership. Additionally, human capital endowment, regional economic production patterns, inter-regional knowledge spillovers, and country institutional effects are relevant for explaining membership in a specific innovation activity club, while agglomeration effects seem to be irrelevant. With respect to the signs, all the variables were as we expected. The positive signs on R&D, HC, DEN, GVA, and SPI mean that regions with higher values for these variables are more likely to belong to a club with a higher innovation activity converging level. The negative sign of INS suggests that higher values for this variable mean a region is more likely to belong to a club with a lower innovation activity converging level. This last finding is reasonable since a higher value for INS means a lower degree of institutional development in the country. Therefore, we can conclude that factors underlined by the knowledge production function approach seem to be relevant for explaining club membership.

[Table 2 about here]

In analysing the effect of each variable on the probability of membership in a specific club, we obtained marginal effects (Table 3). Marginal effects represent the instantaneous rate of change in the probability of belonging to a specific club given a small change in explanatory variables (Long and Fresse, 2014). An overview of the

results suggests that the probability of membership in clubs 3 to 7 is explained quite well by the variables considered in our model. Additionally, the magnitude of marginal effects suggests that R&D, followed by SPI and HC, have the largest impact on club membership. For the most innovative club (Club1+Club2), all the coefficients exhibit the expected signs, but any variable seems to be significant at conventional levels; however, the variables that seem to be the most important factors in determining club membership (R&D, HC and SPI) are relevant if we consider a 15% level of significance. This result could be due to the small sample size since only 8 regions form this club, meaning that the effects that are significant for clubs 3 to 7 are partly significant at the 15% level only. Finally, as stated above, it can be appreciated that DEN¹⁰ does not appear to be a key factor in determining club membership.

[Table 3 about here]

Marginal effects suggest that a small positive change in R&D, HC, GVA, and SPI increases the probability of belonging to more innovative clubs, while it decreases the probability of belonging to the least innovative clubs (Club6 and Club7). For INS, the coefficients of marginal effects exhibit an opposite sign with respect to the rest of the variables, meaning that a small positive change in this variable increases the

¹⁰ Based on the recommendation of an anonymous reviewer, we compare the results of this estimation with an alternative estimation using just DEN instead of DEN in logarithm form. When DEN (instead of the logarithm of DEN) is included in the model, this variable is positive and significant for explaining club membership, but just at the 10% level of significance. However, an overview to the marginal effects, suggest that this variable is relevant at 10% of significance only for explaining the probability of belonging to clubs 4 and 6 and with an impact nearly to zero, while seem to be irrelevant for the majority of the clubs considered. With respect to the rest of the variables in the model, these maintain their sign and significance. The results of this alternative estimation can be provided upon request.

probability of belonging to the least innovative clubs (Club 6 and Club7), while it decreases the probability of belonging to the most innovative clubs (Table 3). When we focus on the magnitude of marginal effects, a clear picture emerges: R&D efforts in the initial period are the most important factor in explaining a region's membership in a specific innovation club. This result is mostly in line with innovation-based growth models and with empirical evidence about the determinants of innovation activity at the regional level, which underline the key role played by R&D resources in promoting innovation activity at the regional level.

All in all, the results of Tables 2 and 3 confirm that initial conditions play a significant role in explaining the formation of clubs and reveal the key role played by R&D efforts in determining the club membership of a region, while we control for the effects of regional structural characteristics.

5. Conclusions

In spite of efforts to promote a true convergence in the EU territory in the last several decades, empirical evidence from different time periods indicates that, rather than an overall convergence, a convergence into groups has been produced. There are theoretical and empirical arguments that support the role of technological capabilities of economies as the driving force for club convergence. In the case of European regions, as some studies show, there are differences in innovation ability and absorption capacity, giving rise to innovation activity clubs.

This paper analyses convergence or divergence in innovation activity among European regions during the 2000s, adding relevant new evidence to the scarce empirical literature on this topic. The main contribution of this study is the application to innovation data of a non-linear model developed by Phillips and Sul (2007) that

endogenously clusters regions. In addition, it contributes to identifying important factors for explaining the formation of innovation convergence clubs.

The empirical analysis raises some issues that are relevant to the process of convergence in innovation activity among regions in the EU. First, our findings reveal that there has not been a process of overall convergence among European regions in innovation activity. Conversely, this paper provides evidence about the existence of seven regional clubs in the EU with different levels of absorptive capacities and innovative ability and different growth dynamics during the analysed period. In other words, European regions appear divided into innovation clubs ranging from high innovation clubs to lagging innovation clubs. The high and intermediate innovation clubs are mainly composed of regions belonging to the Nordic countries and France, Germany, Belgium, Austria, England, and Ireland. The less innovative clubs (Clubs 6 and 7) are mainly formed by regions belonging to Eastern European countries and Portugal. In Spain and Italy, the northern regions belong to intermediate innovation clubs (Clubs 4 and 5) while the southern regions belong to clubs with the lowest number of patents per million inhabitants. Second, it must be remarked that despite clubs maintaining the differences between their transition paths, the different clubs tend to converge toward the average, diminishing the distances between them at the end of the analysed period. This suggests that, although there are still disparities with respect to innovation activity among European regions, these disparities have decreased during the period of our analysis.

Our analysis of the factors determining club membership supports the club convergence hypothesis, underscoring the role of initial conditions in the formation of innovation clubs. In fact, the significance and magnitude of marginal effects for internal R&D efforts guide us to acknowledge the predominant role that initial R&D

expenditure has played in the formation of innovation clubs. A small positive change in R&D expenditures increases the probability of belonging to the high and intermediate clubs while decreasing the probability of belonging to the less innovative clubs. Similarly, initial values of regional structural conditions—that is, human capital and industrial economic structure as well as inter-regional knowledge spillovers and institutional variables—are also relevant for explaining innovation club classification.

The formation of different groups of regions with respect to their innovation production reflects different initial conditions and differences in their structural regional conditions. In other words, the different growth paths in innovation performance in the European regions mostly occur with differences in investment in research and development, but also differences in available human capital and the effects of the surrounding regions.

Our findings have interesting implications for policy-making due to the relevant role of innovation in the generation of economic growth. The existence of disparities in innovative activities between regions might cause increasing inequalities in growth in the future. Thus, from a policy point of view, enhancing financial support (through R&D expenditure) for innovation activities, along with the adoption of measures aimed at investing in knowledge diffusion and absorption, could contribute to improving innovation abilities, reducing the disparities across regions, and favouring convergence in European territories. However, these measures may not have the same impact for different regions. Although our findings point to the importance of R&D in regional innovation, it is not the only factor that explains innovation and, therefore, these other determinants must be taken into account in the formulation of policy. Thus, policy-makers should consider the different characteristics (initial conditions and structural conditions) of regions (or groups of regions) in order to apply differentiated innovation

policies, meaning that a “one-size-fits-all” policy (Tödtling and Trippl, 2005; Camagni and Capello, 2013; Capello and Lenzi, 2014) may be inappropriate if the target is to reduce disparities among European regions.

Appendix A. Sample.

The sample used in this study comprises 180 regions in 26 countries, including Austria (nine regions), Belgium (three regions), Bulgaria (two regions), Cyprus (one region), Czech Republic (eight regions), Denmark (one region), Estonia (one region), France (twenty-two regions), Finland (four regions), Germany (sixteen regions), Hungary (seven regions), Italy (twenty regions), Ireland (one region), Latvia (one region), Lithuania (one region), Luxembourg (one region), Netherlands (eleven regions), Poland (sixteen regions), Portugal (five regions), Romania (four regions), Spain (seventeen regions), Slovenia (one region), Slovakia (four regions), Sweden (eight regions), and the United Kingdom (twelve regions). The regions are NUTS2, NUTS1 and NUTS0; the regions and the codes for each region are given below.

Country	Regions
Austria	(AT11) Burgenland; (AT12) Niederösterreich; (AT13) Wien; (AT21) Kärnten; (AT22) Steiermark; (AT31) Oberösterreich; (AT32) Salzburg; (AT33) Tirol; (AT34) Vorarlberg
Belgium	(BE1) Region de Bruxelles-Capitale / Brussels Hoofdstedelijk Gewest; (BE2) Vlaams Gewest; (BE3) Region wallonne
Bulgaria	(BG3) Severna i yugoiztochna; (BG4) Yugozapadna i yuzhna tsentralna
Cyprus	(CY0) Kypros
Czech Republic	(CZ01) Praha; (CZ02) Strední Cechy; (CZ03) Jihozápad; (CZ04) Severozápad; (CZ05) Severovýchod; (CZ06) Jihovýchod; (CZ07) Strední Morava; (CZ08) Moravskoslezsko
Denmark	(DK0) Danmark
Estonia	(EE0) Eesti
France	(FR10) Île de France; (FR21) Champagne-Ardenne; (FR22) Picardie; (FR23) Haute-Normandie; (FR24) Centre; (FR25) Basse-Normandie; (FR26) Bourgogne; (FR30) Nord - Pas-de-Calais; (FR41) Lorraine; (FR42) Alsace; (FR43) Franche-Comté; (FR51) Pays de la Loire; (FR52) Bretagne; (FR53) Poitou-Charentes; (FR61) Aquitaine; (FR62) Midi-Pyrénées; (FR63) Limousin; (FR71) Rhône-Alpes; (FR72) Auvergne; (FR81) Languedoc-Roussillon; (FR82) Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur; (FR83) Corse
Finland	(FI19) Länsi-Suomi; (FI1B) Helsinki-Uusimaa; (FI1C) Etelä-Suomi; (FI1D) Pohjois- ja Itä-Suomi
Germany	(DE1) Baden-Württemberg; (DE2) Bayern; (DE3) Berlin; (DE4) Brandenburg;

	(DE5) Bremen; (DE6) Hamburg; (DE7) Hessen; (DE8) Mecklenburg-Vorpommern; (DE9) Niedersachsen; (DEA) Nordrhein-Westfalen; (DEB) Rheinland-Pfalz; (DEC) Saarland; (DED)Sachsen; (DEE)Sachsen-Anhalt; (DEF)Schleswig-Holstein; (DEG)Thüringen.
Hungary	(HU10) Közép-Magyarország; (HU21) Közép-Dunántúl; (HU22) Nyugat-Dunántúl; (HU23) Dél-Dunántúl; (HU31) Észak-Magyarország; (HU32) Észak-Alföld; (HU33)Dél-Alföld
Italy	(ITC1) Piemonte; (ITC2) Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste; (ITC3) Liguria; (ITC4) Lombardia; (ITF1) Abruzzo; (ITF2) Molise; (ITF3) Campania; (ITF4) Puglia; (ITF5) Basilicata; (ITF6) Calabria; (ITG1) Sicilia; (ITG2) Sardegna; (ITH1) Provincia Autonoma di Bolzano/Bozen; (ITH2) Provincia Autonoma di Trento; (ITH4) Friuli-Venezia Giulia; (ITH5) Emilia-Romagna; (ITI1) Toscana; (ITI2) Umbria; (ITI3) Marche; (ITI4) Lazio
Ireland	(IE0) Éire
Latvia	(LV0) Latvija
Lithuania	(LT0) Lietuva
Luxembourg	(LU0) Luxembourg
Malta	(MT0) Malta
Netherlands	(NL11) Groningen; (NL12) Friesland; (NL13) Drenthe; (NL21) Overijssel; (NL22) Gelderland; (NL23) Flevoland; (NL31) Utrecht; (NL32) Noord-Holland; (NL34) Zeeland; (NL41) Noord-Brabant; (NL42) Limburg
Poland	(PL11) Łódzkie; (PL12) Mazowieckie; (PL21) Malopolskie; (PL22) Slaskie; (PL31) Lubelskie; (PL32) Podkarpackie; (PL33) Swietokrzyskie; (PL34) Podlaskie; (PL41) Wielkopolskie; (PL42) Zachodniopomorskie; (PL43) Lubuskie; (PL51) Dolnoslaskie; (PL52) Opolskie; (PL61) Kujawsko-Pomorskie; (PL62) Warminsko-Mazurskie; (PL63) Pomorskie
Portugal	(PT11) Norte; (PT15) Algarve; (PT16) Centro; (PT17) Área Metropolitana de Lisboa; (PT18) Alentejo
Romania	(RO1) Macroregiunea unu; (RO2) Macroregiunea doi; (RO3) Macroregiunea trei; (RO4) Macroregiunea patru
Spain	(ES11) Galicia; (ES12) Principado de Asturias; (ES13) Cantabria; (ES21) País Vasco; (ES22) Comunidad Foral de Navarra; (ES23) La Rioja; (ES24) Aragón; (ES30) Comunidad de Madrid; (ES41) Castilla y León; (ES42) Castilla-la Mancha; (ES43) Extremadura; (ES51) Cataluña; (ES52) Comunidad Valenciana; (ES53) Illes Balears; (ES61) Andalucía; (ES62) Región de Murcia; (ES70) Canarias

Slovenia	(SI0) Slovenija
Slovakia	(SK01) Bratislavský kraj; (SK02) Západné Slovensko; (SK03) Stredné Slovensko; (SK04) Východné Slovensko
Sweden	(SE11) Stockholm; (SE12) Östra Mellansverige; (SE21) Småland med öarna; (SE22) Sydsverige; (SE23) Västsverige; (SE31) Norra Mellansverige; (SE32) Mellersta Norrland; (SE33) Övre Norrland
United Kingdom	(UKC) North East; (UKD) North West; (UKE) Yorkshire and The Humber; (UKF) East Midlands; (UKG) West Midlands; (UKH) East of England; (UKI) London; (UKJ) South East; (UKK) South West; (UKL) Wales; (UKM) Scotland; (UKN) Northern Ireland

Appendix B. Convergence clubs.

Club1	AT34, NL41
Club2	FI1B, SE11, DE1, SE22, DE2, AT31
Club3	FI19, DE7, ITH4, AT22, SE12, FR71, DEB, DEA, DE6, FR10, SE23, AT33, DK0, NL42, FI1C, DE3, DE9, DEF, AT32, FI1D, ITH1, FR72
Club4	AT12, BE2, FR42, DEC, ITH5, AT13, SE21, SE31, DEG, LU0, NL21, FR52, UKJ, NL31, FR43, AT21, BE1, FR82, UKK, DED, ES24, NL22, FR62, ITC4, SE33, ITC1, UKH, DE4, FR23, DE5, FR24
Club5	NL32, BE3, ES21, UKF, FR21, FR26, FR51, UKG, ITI3, ITC3, FR61, ITI1, NL23, AT11, ES22, FR41, ES51, NL34, UKI, ITH2, SE32, FR22, SI0, FR81, HU10, ES30, IE0, ITC2, UKM, UKC
Club6	FR63, NL13, DE8, UKD, FR30, UKN, NL11, NL12, FR25, FR53, UKL, UKE, DEE, CZ01, CZ06, CZ05, PL12, PL11, PL21, EE0, ITI2, ITI4, ES52, ES62, ITF1, ES13, PL43, HU33, CZ02, ES23, LV0, PL51, ES11, CZ07, ES61, SK01, ES53, HU21, LT0, PL41, PL63, PL22, PT18, HU22, CZ04
Club7	ES41, PT16, ITF5, ITF3, ITF6, PL52, ES42, PL42, FR83, PT11, SK02, RO3, CZ08, BG4, CZ03, PL61, HU23, PL32, ITG2, SK04, PL33, PL31, HU31, ITF2, ITF4, ES12, PT17, HU32, ES70, ITG1, PT15, PL34, RO2, CY0, PL62, SK03, RO4, RO1, BG3, ES43

Appendix C. Descriptive statistics for dependent and explanatory variables.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Club</i>	176	2.85	1.50	1.00	6.00
<i>R&D</i>	174	1.23	0.95	0.06	5.54
<i>HC</i>	171	15.00	6.14	5.50	30.20

<i>DEN</i>	174	305.13	747.79	3.30	6119.30
<i>GVA</i>	176	22.53	7.22	6.07	40.79
<i>SPI</i>	176	5.21	3.66	0.00	17.20
<i>INS</i>	173	28.28	17.58	1.00	67.00

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Table 1. Convergence club classification.

Club	No. of regions	t Statistic	β Coefficient	Patens per million inhabitant (2012)
Club 1	2	0.2328	0.2021	543.0
Club 2	6	0.8751	0.1189	364.0
Club 3	22	-0.6001	-0.0908	181.1
Club 4	31	-0.4103	-0.0650	104.6
Club 5	30	-0.8776	-0.3286	57.2
Club 6	45	-0.7391	-0.1199	22.0
Club 7	40	-1.2388	-0.2248	5.7

Figure 1. Convergence clubs.

Figure 2. Transition paths.

Table 2. Ordered logit regression results.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error*	z
<i>R&D</i>	1.598***	0.314	5.10
<i>HC</i>	0.071**	0.032	2.25
<i>DEN^a</i>	0.163	0.144	1.13
<i>GVA</i>	0.047*	0.024	1.93
<i>SPI</i>	0.234***	0.043	5.39
<i>INS</i>	-0.034***	0.011	-3.01
No. of observations	168		
Wald (p-value)	98.56 (0.00)		
Pseudo R2	0.3214		

* White heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors in parentheses. ^a Variable in logarithms. Estimations obtained by using the Stata' command ologit. *** p < 0.01 ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Table 3. Marginal effects on probabilities.

Variable	Club1 +Club2	Club 3	Club 4	Club 5	Club 6	Club 7
<i>R&D</i>	0.004 ^o (0.003)	0.046 *** (0.017)	0.197*** (0.053)	0.151 *** (0.054)	-0.293 *** (0.071)	-0.104 (0.025)
<i>HC</i>	0.0002 ^o (0.0001)	0.002** (0.0009)	0.009** (0.004)	0.007 ^o (0.004)	-0.013** (0.006)	-0.005** (0.002)
<i>DEN</i>	0.0004 (0.0005)	0.005 (0.005)	0.020 (0.018)	0.015 (0.014)	-0.030 (0.026)	-0.011 (0.010)
<i>GVA</i>	0.0001 (0.0001)	0.001* (0.0008)	0.006* (0.003)	0.004 ^o (0.003)	-0.009* (0.005)	-0.003* (0.002)
<i>SPI</i>	0.0006 ^o (0.0004)	0.007*** (0.003)	0.029*** (0.007)	0.022*** (0.008)	-0.043*** (0.010)	- (0.004)
<i>INS</i>	-0.0001 (0.0001)	-0.0010* (0.0005)	-0.004*** (0.001)	-0.003** (0.001)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.002** (0.001)

White heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors in parenthesis. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1, ^o p < 0.15. Marginal effects calculated in Stata using the command `mchange`. Marginal effects are calculated at the mean of all variables.